

exceeded 250 hoppers/hill. Populations of natural enemies like mirid bug, wolf spider, and coccinellid beetles were higher in unsprayed fields. □

Effect of neem seed bitters (NSB) on green leafhopper (GLH) feeding

R. C. Saxena and M. E. M. Boncodin,
Entomology Department, IIRRI

A simple process has been developed at IIRRI to extract the "bitters" (limonoids) from neem seed kernel. Using an electronic device, we monitored the feeding behavior of newly emerged GLH *Nephotettix virescens* females on 21-d-old TN1 rice seedlings that had been treated systemically by overnight root immersion or by dipping the foliage in a 2,500 ppm NSB aqueous solution for 25 s.

During a 3-h observation, waveform

patterns (see figure) showed that duration of phloem feeding was significantly reduced in neem-treated seedlings (see table). The decrease in phloem feeding was accompanied by a corresponding significant increase in frequency of probing, salivation period, and xylem feeding. If GLH feeds less in the phloem, it has less probability of acquiring or transmitting tungro viruses. □

Waveforms electronically recorded during *N. virescens* feeding on TN1 rice plants, IIRRI, 1987. a = control, b = 2500 ppm NSB-systemic, c = 2500 ppm NSB-foliar. P = probe, S = salivation, Pi = phloem ingestion, R = rest, Xi = xylem ingestion.

Events in 3-h feeding by *N. virescens* females on TN1 rice seedlings treated with 2,500 ppm NSB solution.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Treatment	Probes (no.)	Salivation (min)	Phloem ingestion (min)	Xylem ingestion (min)	Total ingestion (min)
Systemic	25 a	20.7 a	27 b	23 a	50 a
Foliar	24 a	15.2 ab	33 b	27 a	60 a
Control	13 b	9.6 b	77 a	1 b	78 a

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Effect of neem seed treatment on rice seedling vigor and survival of brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

A.A. Kareem, R.C. Saxena, M.E.M. Boncodin, Entomology Department; and V. Krishnasamy and D.V. Seshu, IRTP, IIRRI

The principal bitters of neem, particularly azadirachtin, are known to be systemically translocated through the roots. We evaluated seed treatment with crude neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) or neem cake (NC) as a BPH or GLH control measure for young seedlings. We also measured the effect of neem treatment on seed germination and seedling vigor.

In one treatment, healthy seeds of TN1, IR36, and IR42 were soaked in 2.5, 5, or 10% aqueous NSKE solution for 24 h, then incubated for 48 h. In

Table 1. Effect of seed treatment with crude NSKE and NC on BPH and GLH survival.^a IIRRI, 1987.

Neem concentration (%)	Nymphs becoming adults (%)		
	BPH on TN1	GLH on TN1	GLH on IR42
NSKE			
2.5	46.7 b	57.0 b	6.7 a
5.0	63.3 cd	44.3 b	10.0 a
10.0	30.0 a	6.7 a	10.0 a
NC			
1.0	50.0 bc	50.0 b	6.7 a
2.0	30.0 a	30.0 b	13.3 a
0 (check)	70.0 d	70.0 b	36.7 a

^aAv of 3 replications, 10 first-instar nymphs/replication. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.